

BLUEVISION

D7.1 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Sustainable predictive maintenance for circular material preservation and human-centric remote-operations in maritime critical infrastructures via augmented reality and digital twins

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Communication and Dissemination (CD) Plan

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Abbreviations¹

Abbreviations	
EC	European Commission
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
ECVET	European Credit System for Vocational Education and Training
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
IDE	Impact, Dissemination, Exploitation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
ROL	Results Ownership List
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SPMM	Sustainable Predictive Maritime Maintenance
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
WP	Work Package

¹ abbreviations are letter combinations which summarise/abbreviate a longer set of words; terminology is not limited to abbreviations, but goes beyond and captures words/terms which are specific to the project and the project context

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Executive summary

The Communication and Dissemination (CD) Plan sets the overall strategy for how BLUEVISION will ensure that its results are visible, accessible, and sustainably used during the three year project duration. It outlines the project's approach to communicating achievements, disseminating knowledge, and exploiting outcomes for long-term impact in science, industry, society, and policymaking.

The plan follows a three-phase approach, namely Creation, Growth, and Exploitation, ensuring that activities evolve in step with the project's lifecycle. It defines coordination mechanisms, roles, and performance indicators to maintain coherence and accountability across the consortium.

Through a unified set of tools, including a strong visual identity, online platforms, social media channels, newsletters, and promotional materials, the project will foster engagement and collaboration with diverse stakeholders. Exploitation activities will follow a structured process involving exploitation surveys, SWOT analyses, workshops, and business model development, ensuring that the project's outputs are translated into practical value and sustainable use.

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Introduction

This Communication and Dissemination Plan provides the strategic framework for implementing BLUEVISION's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. It defines the plan's purpose, scope, and alignment with Erasmus+ objectives, including Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Open Science, and inclusivity.

The document further serves as a practical guide for project partners, ensuring that all actions related to visibility, outreach, and result exploitation are coherent, measurable, and strategically coordinated. It establishes how the consortium will communicate project objectives and progress, disseminate results to relevant audiences, and promote their uptake and reuse beyond the project's lifetime.

The plan also sets out the tools, indicators, and tracking mechanisms that will support its implementation. The following sections describe the structure of the plan, outline its objectives, and detail how BLUEVISION will ensure transparency, alignment, and long-term impact through an integrated approach to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

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1 Structure of the document

This document is organised to provide a clear and logical overview of the BLUEVISION project's approach to dissemination, exploitation, and impact. Section 1 presents the overall structure of the document, describing how the information is organised and how it connects to the project's communication and impact strategy. Section 2 defines the purpose and scope of the CD Plan, outlining its guiding principles and strategic intent. Section 3 sets out the project's overall IDE strategy, objectives, and phased approach, describing how activities will evolve throughout the project's lifecycle. Section 4 details the implementation activities for communication, dissemination, and exploitation, structured around the 4Cs principles: Creation, Curation, Customisation, and Control. It also defines the coordination mechanisms, roles, and timing for each activity. Section 5 describes the tools, channels, and branding elements that will be used to implement the strategy, including visual identity, promotional materials, the project website, online learning platform, social media, and newsletters. Section 6 focuses on monitoring and evaluation, outlining how progress will be tracked through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Together, these sections form a coherent structure that connects the strategic, operational, and evaluative dimensions of dissemination, exploitation, and communication. Sections 2-3 establish the vision, purpose, and objectives of the CD Plan, explaining the "why" behind the strategy. Sections 4-5 outline the implementation framework and partner responsibilities, defining the "how" and "who." Section 6 presents the tools and metrics that will measure progress, representing the "with what" and "how well." Section 7 focuses on the "what next," ensuring that all project results are effectively communicated, disseminated, protected, and translated into long-term impact.

2 Definitions and conceptual framework

This section defines the concepts of Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) as applied in the BLUEVISION project, in line with the European Commission's 2023 guidelines². These definitions provide a shared framework for all partners to ensure consistency across project activities, reporting, and external engagement.

- **Communication** refers to promoting the project and its activities to diverse audiences, including the public, to raise awareness and demonstrate the value of EU-funded research and innovation.
- **Dissemination** means making project results available to stakeholders who can best use them, such as researchers, industry representatives, and policymakers, through appropriate channels, including open access publications, events, and repositories.
- **Exploitation** refers to the uptake and use of project results for further research, innovation, policy development, or commercialisation, ensuring their long-term sustainability and societal impact.

² Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/289075>

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Figure 1: European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter

This plan applies exclusively to external communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Internal communication among consortium partners is managed separately under the project’s governance and management procedures. As a living document, the CD Plan will be continuously updated to reflect project progress, stakeholder feedback, and emerging opportunities for impact throughout the project’s lifetime.

3 Objectives

The BLUEVISION Communication and Dissemination Plan is fully aligned with the project’s overarching ambition to reduce human risk, environmental damage, and economic losses in maritime critical infrastructures by accelerating the adoption of Sustainable Predictive Maritime Maintenance (SPMM) solutions. Acting as an enabling framework, the CD Plan connects BLUEVISION’s technical outputs – micro-credentials, digital twins, augmented reality tools, and an industrial metaverse – with real-world uptake. Through coordinated communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, the plan will increase project visibility, mobilise stakeholders across industry, training, and policy, and ensure that BLUEVISION results are accessible, reusable and sustainable beyond the project’s lifecycle.

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Building on this foundation, the CD Plan will directly contribute to the achievement of BLUEVISION's core objectives, as outlined below:

Upskill the maritime workforce and embed SPMM in vocational pathways

- **Communicate and promote** the delivery of seven European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) / European Credit System for Vocational Education and Training (ECVET) aligned micro-courses designed for Initial Vocational Education and Training (IVET) and Continuing Vocational Education and Training (CVET) portability and targeted at frontline maritime workers and technicians.
- **Disseminate** the full micro-credential framework and make it accessible through open platforms and various channels to maximise reuse.
- **Ensure visibility and reuse** of learning materials by publishing them under open licences, integrating them into partner training offers, and promoting recognition through accreditation and ECTS/ECVET pathways.

Empower training and entrepreneurial capacities across regions

- **Promote the establishment** of seven entrepreneurial maritime incubators that combine industry, academia and training providers to accelerate applied R&D, and startup activity in SPMM.
- **Communicate the training and empowerment** of at least 250 SPMM trainers through targeted campaigns, trainer academies and multiplier events to ensure broad capacity for course delivery and local scaling.
- **Reuse best practices** from previous successfully conducted projects to enhance visibility and reach.

Support pan-EU skill portability and occupational standardisation

- **Disseminate the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles** developed in alignment with National Qualification Frameworks to enable cross-border recognition and labour mobility.
- **Promote stakeholder endorsement** (industry, Vocational Education and Training (VET) providers) and document pathways for accreditation and credit transfer in clear guidance.
- **Accelerate the adoption of digital twins, Augmented Reality (AR), and the industrial metaverse for SPMM**
- **Communicate the development and availability** of the SPMM skills ecosystem platform and the integrated maritime industrial metaverse with digital twins for hands-on learning.
- **Disseminate pilot results** from 200 work-based learning apprenticeships and demonstrators to industry audiences, highlighting safety, environmental, and economic benefits.

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Promote inclusive, sustainable career pathways and innovation

- **Communicate initiatives** that support diversity and inclusion to, for instance, increase female participation in maritime deep-tech roles.
- **Disseminate success stories** that help learners translate micro-credentials into recognised career pathways and entrepreneurial opportunities.

Reinforce BLUEVISION's societal and policy impact

- **Disseminate evidence-based recommendations** and impact assessments that demonstrate how SPMM reduces fatalities, environmental incidents and economic losses.
- **Promote cross sectoral collaboration** between technical, social science, and regulatory stakeholders to ensure human-centric, ethically compliant deployment of SPMM technologies.
- **Increase visibility of results** through publications, datasets, or conference presentations to strengthen European leadership in safe, sustainable maritime digitalisation.

The CD Plan is implemented in three interconnected phases: Creation, Growth, and Exploitation. Together, these phases form a coherent and adaptive pathway that links BLUEVISION's vision - the widespread adoption of Sustainable Predictive Maintenance (SPMM) in maritime critical infrastructures - with measurable impact. The phased approach ensures that communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities evolve in parallel with project progress, moving from awareness building and stakeholder engagement to piloting, validation, and result uptake, and finally to long term recognition and institutionalisation. By structuring activities this way, BLUEVISION creates a continuous impact pathway that transforms its educational and technical outputs – micro-courses, incubator blueprints, the SPMM Competence Framework, and the skills ecosystem platform with digital twins - into practical safety, environmental, and economic benefits for workers, organisations, and policy frameworks across the maritime sector.

Creation phase

In the Creation phase, BLUEVISION will establish visibility, credibility, and the foundational assets required for SPMM adoption across maritime infrastructures. Activities will focus on producing and publishing the seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-courses and the full micro-credential framework on open platforms, ensuring materials are released under open licences and integrated into partner training offers to maximise accessibility and reuse. During this phase, the project will prepare the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles for consultation with National Qualification Framework authorities and VET providers and will design the operational and conceptual blueprint for the seven entrepreneurial maritime incubators to attract industry, academia, and training partners. Communications will also introduce the SPMM skills ecosystem platform and the integrated maritime industrial metaverse with digital twins, and document initial accreditation pathways and stakeholder engagement plans so that learning pathways, incubator services and platform features are ready for piloting and endorsement.

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Growth phase

The Growth phase will deepen stakeholder engagement, scale capacity, and validate BLUEVISION outputs through hands-on activities and broader dissemination. Efforts will concentrate on rolling out the micro-courses in IVET and CVET contexts, localising and translating materials, and running trainer academies and multiplier events to empower at least 250 SPMM trainers and ensure local delivery capacity. Seven entrepreneurial incubators will be operationalised, drawing on best practices from prior successful projects to accelerate applied R&D and startup activity. The SPMM skills ecosystem platform and industrial metaverse will be tested and iterated through demonstrators and 200 work based learning apprenticeships, with pilot results and case studies disseminated to VET networks and policy stakeholders to highlight safety, environmental and economic benefits and to support accreditation and credit transfer pathways.

Exploitation phase

The Exploitation phase will secure long term uptake, recognition, and societal impact by embedding BLUEVISION results into institutional practice and policy. Activities will promote formal adoption of the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles via different channels and stakeholder endorsement, support partners in integrating micro-credentials into training offers, and publish final operational models and guidance for incubator replication and platform sustainability. Consolidated, evidence-based recommendations and impact assessments will be disseminated to policymakers and industry to demonstrate how SPMM reduces fatalities, environmental incidents, and economic losses. Success stories, publications, datasets, and conference presentations will be used to attract partners and investors, foster cross-sectoral collaboration between technical, social science and regulatory stakeholders, and ensure that BLUEVISION outputs remain accessible, reusable and impactful beyond the project lifetime.

4 Implementation activities

The implementation activities translate the CD Plan into practical actions that reach the right audiences, deliver consistent messages, and generate measurable and sustainable impact. Activities are organised to ensure that BLUEVISION's educational and technical outputs - the seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-courses, the micro-credential framework, the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles, entrepreneurial incubators, the SPMM skills ecosystem platform with digital twins and the Women in Maritime Tech accelerator - are developed, validated and positioned for long-term uptake across the maritime sector.

Implementation follows a phased timeline aligned with project milestones, ensuring that IDE actions evolve as results emerge and stakeholder engagement deepens. Early activities will prioritise production and open publication of the micro-credential framework and the preparation of the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles for stakeholder consultation. Subsequent activities will focus on trainer empowerment, incubator operationalisation and piloting of the SPMM skills ecosystem platform with apprenticeships, while later actions will concentrate on formal recognition, institutional embedding and dissemination of consolidated policy recommendations.

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At least one representative from each consortium partner will actively participate in regular alignment meetings in order to align messaging, monitor progress, integrate stakeholder feedback and maintain coherence across channels and languages. Partners will contribute according to their expertise by proposing content, supporting outreach and facilitating local integration of materials. A combined centralised and decentralised communication model will be applied: central coordination will manage core assets, branding and strategic messaging, while partners will amplify outreach through their institutional networks to extend regional and sectoral reach. Regular IDE team meetings will review progress, align activities with project outputs and ensure that monitoring and evaluation feedback informs timely adjustments to maximise impact.

The implementation framework puts the CD Plan into practice by aligning actions with target audiences, reinforcing consistent messaging, and supporting measurable, long-term impact.

4.1 The 4Cs principles

The implementation of the CD Plan is guided by four core principles: Creation, Curation, Customisation, and Control.

Creation focuses on producing open, high quality micro-course content, the micro-credential framework and the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles, ensuring their readiness for validation, recognition, and uptake. Curation ensures that all outputs meet agreed quality standards and are made available through trusted, multilingual open platforms to maximise accessibility and reuse, and long-term sustainability. Customisation allows materials and engagement formats to be adapted to the needs of frontline maritime workers, VET trainers, incubator partners and policy stakeholders, and supports inclusive measures such as the Women in Maritime Tech accelerator, thereby increasing relevance and adoption across target groups. Control establishes monitoring and feedback loops to track uptake, accreditation progress and stakeholder endorsement, enabling evidence-based adjustments throughout implementation and supporting data-driven decision making.

4.2 Communication activities

Communication activities will raise awareness of BLUEVISION's aims and outputs among industry, VET providers, policymakers and maritime workers. Central communications will present the micro-course offer and the micro-credential framework, explain pathways for ECTS/ECVET recognition and promote the incubator concept and the SPMM skills ecosystem platform, alongside regular content dissemination activities.

Key communication activities include:

- Presenting the seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-course offer and the overall micro-credential framework to target audiences.
- Clarifying pathways for ECTS/ECVET recognition and IVET/CVET portability.
- Promoting the seven entrepreneurial incubators and their role in applied R&D and startup activity.
- Introducing the SPMM skills ecosystem platform and the integrated maritime industrial metaverse with digital twins for hands-on learning.
- Emphasising the safety, environmental and economic benefits of SPMM in all messaging.

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- Highlighting opportunities for career development, mobility and trainer empowerment.
- Delivering communications in multiple languages and adapt content to stakeholder needs and levels of expertise.
- Supporting partners in integrating BLUEVISION materials into local training offers and accreditation pathways.

4.3 Dissemination activities

Dissemination activities ensure that BLUEVISION's micro-credential framework, the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles, and evidence from pilots and apprenticeships are shared with the stakeholders best placed to use them. These actions promote open access to learning and qualification materials, support accreditation and cross-border recognition, and document incubator operational models and best practices to enable replication and institutional uptake.

Key dissemination activities include:

Clustering activities

- Engage with VET networks, ports, shipyards, and equipment providers to align dissemination efforts and identify opportunities for joint uptake of SPMM materials.
- Share incubator operational models and lessons learned with regional and sectoral networks to support replication and scalability.

Collaboration with EU-funded projects

- Establish links with complementary EU projects, organisations, and initiatives to exchange methodologies and promote the micro-credential framework and SPMM Competence Framework across broader networks.
- Coordinate joint dissemination where appropriate to amplify messages about accreditation pathways and skill portability.

Conferences and sector events

- Present the micro-credential framework, SPMM Competence Framework, and pilot findings at relevant maritime, VET, and policy events to reach industry, training providers, and qualification authorities.
- Use conference presentations and panels to highlight practical benefits from the 200 work-based apprenticeships and demonstrators.

Education and training events

- Roll out seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-courses in IVET and CVET settings and promote trainer academies to build delivery capacity.
- Disseminate guidance on integrating micro-credentials into partner training offers and on pathways for ECTS/ECVET recognition.

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Meetings and stakeholder consultations

- Conduct targeted consultations with National Qualification Framework authorities and VET providers to support endorsement and accreditation of the Occupational Profiles.
- Organise co-creation and stakeholder meetings with ports, shipyards, and industry partners to validate incubator services and platform features.

Other dissemination outputs

- Publish the micro-credential framework, SPMM Competence Framework, and Occupational Profiles on open, multilingual platforms under open licences to maximise accessibility and reuse.
- Synthesize pilot findings from the 200 apprenticeships into accessible reports and case studies documenting implementation lessons and practical benefits for practitioners and policymakers.

Other scientific collaboration

- Promote joint publications and collaborative outputs that arise from pilots and apprenticeships, ensuring results are discoverable through trusted open repositories.
- Share datasets and evidence underpinning policy recommendations to support transparent, evidence-based decision-making.

All dissemination actions will prioritise open access and clear, accessible communication to facilitate reuse, accreditation, and cross-border mobility of skills and qualifications across the maritime sector. Open-access dissemination will use trusted repositories such as Zenodo and GitHub to support transparency, reusability, and long-term value of project results.

4.4 Exploitation activities

The exploitation phase focuses on maximising the use, impact, and sustainability of the project. It aims to maximise the use, impact, and sustainability of BLUEVISION's results. Activities ensure that project outputs create societal and economic value, support long-term capacity building in Sustainable Predictive Maintenance (SPMM) across the maritime sector, and are embedded into institutional practice and qualification systems.

Framework and tools for exploitation

- Promote formal adoption of the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles through targeted engagement with National Qualification Framework authorities and VET providers to enable cross-border recognition and labour mobility.
- Support integration of the seven ECTS/ECVET-aligned micro-courses and the micro-credential framework into partner training offers to secure IVET and CVET portability.
- Prepare incubator operational guidance and sustainability options for the seven entrepreneurial maritime incubators to facilitate replication and institutional uptake after project completion

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- Advance the SPMM skills ecosystem platform's sustainability plan to enable continued access to the industrial metaverse and digital twins for training and applied learning.

Knowledge valorisation and training

- Assist partners in embedding micro-credentials and occupational profiles into curricula and continuing professional development pathways, ensuring that training leads to recognised qualifications and career progression.
- Provide guidance and materials to support trainer empowerment and institutional adoption, enabling the 250 SPMM trainers to deliver validated courses across regions.
- Document and disseminate practical implementation guidance and lessons learned from piloting to support wider uptake by VET providers and industry training centres.

Post-pilot support and talent development

- Consolidate evidence and lessons from the 200 work-based learning apprenticeships and demonstrators into actionable recommendations that support post pilot mentoring, career guidance, and follow on learning opportunities.
- Facilitate pathways for apprentices and trained technicians to translate micro-credentials into recognised career routes, supporting employability and mobility.

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration

- Engage industry, ports, shipyards, equipment providers, VET networks and policy makers to identify, and activate exploitation pathways for SPMM solutions, competence frameworks and incubator services.
- Promote partnerships between training providers, incubators and industry to enable joint deployment, secondments, and knowledge exchange that sustain use of BLUEVISION outputs.
- Encourage endorsement by relevant stakeholders to strengthen accreditation, credit transfer mechanisms, and institutional recognition.

Commercialisation and sustainability

- Develop and communicate business model options and sustainability scenarios for incubators and the SPMM skills ecosystem platform to support continued operation, replication, and scaling.
- Share consolidated, evidence-based impact assessments and policy recommendations with industry and policy stakeholders to demonstrate how SPMM contributes to reducing fatalities, environmental incidents and economic losses, thereby creating incentives for adoption and investment.
- Ensure exploitation activities adhere to human-centric and inclusive principles, including measures to sustain the Women in Maritime Tech accelerator and promote equitable access to training and career opportunities.

All exploitation actions will be coordinated with partners and qualification authorities to maximise recognition, institutional embedding, and long-term societal impact of BLUEVISION results.

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4.5 Target audience

A clear understanding of target audiences is essential for tailoring BLUEVISION's IDE activities to their needs and motivations. The CD Plan is stakeholder-driven, ensuring that messages, formats, and channels are adapted to each group's expectations, level of expertise and role in the maritime (SPMM) ecosystem.

Primary target group

Frontline maritime workers and technicians are the principal audience for BLUEVISION. These individuals will directly benefit from the seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-courses and the micro-credential framework, and the CD activities will prioritise clear, practical guidance on how micro-credentials translate into recognised skills and career pathways. Trainers and VET providers who will deliver and accredit the micro-courses are also part of this primary group, as their capacity to adopt and integrate the materials is critical for IVET and CVET portability.

Secondary target group

Incubator partners, industry stakeholders (ports, shipyards, equipment manufacturers) and employers form the secondary audience. Their engagement is essential to operationalise the seven entrepreneurial maritime incubators, host work-based learning apprenticeships, validate demonstrators, and create pathways for employment and commercial uptake of SPMM solutions. Communications for this group will emphasise operational models, business cases and practical benefits for safety, environmental performance, and cost reduction.

Additional stakeholder groups

Qualification authorities and National Qualification Framework (NQF) representatives are targeted to secure endorsement and cross-border recognition of the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles. Policymakers and institutional decision-makers are engaged to receive evidence-based recommendations and impact assessments that support policy alignment and institutional embedding. Ecosystem catalysts such as technology parks, incubators, clusters, and professional associations are addressed as multipliers for replication and scaling. Finally, underrepresented groups and the wider public are included through targeted inclusion measures (notably the Women in Maritime Tech accelerator) and outreach that raises awareness of career opportunities and societal benefits.

The CD Plan will tailor engagement actions, materials, and channels to each group to ensure relevance and uptake: practical accreditation guidance and trainer support for primary audiences; operational guidance and pilot evidence for industry and incubator partners; and policy briefs and consolidated impact evidence for qualification authorities and policymakers. Multilingual delivery and accessible formats will be used throughout to maximise reach and cross-border applicability.

The table below presents the stakeholder engagement strategy that ensures effective, inclusive, and targeted communication, dissemination, and exploitation of BLUEVISION results. It identifies the main stakeholder groups relevant to the maritime (SPMM) ecosystem and summarises the specific engagement actions, activities and channels tailored to each audience. This structured approach ensures that all groups from frontline maritime workers and trainers to industry partners, qualification

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authorities, policymakers and the wider public are reached through appropriate formats and platforms, fostering collaboration, visibility and long-term impact across the sector.

Stakeholder group	Engagement actions and activities	Main communication and dissemination channels
Frontline maritime workers and technicians	Participation in the seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-courses; involvement in work-based learning apprenticeships; contribution to feedback rounds on course relevance and usability; engagement in awareness activities highlighting safety, environmental and economic benefits of SPMM.	Project website, SPMM skills ecosystem platform, multilingual training materials, partner VET channels, social media (LinkedIn), newsletters, on-site training sessions.
Trainers and VET providers	Engagement in trainer academies and multiplier events; integration of micro-credentials into IVET and CVET offers; participation in consultations on the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles.	Project website, (institutional) newsletters, workshops, webinars, social media (LinkedIn), targeted mailings, VET networks.
Industry stakeholders (ports, shipyards, equipment manufacturers)	Participation in incubator activities, pilot demonstrations and work-based apprenticeships; review of operational models; contribution to validation of SPMM Competence Framework; engagement in discussions on safety, environmental and economic benefits of SPMM.	Direct outreach, industry events, LinkedIn, newsletters, project website, stakeholder meetings, sector conferences.
Entrepreneurial maritime incubators and innovation actors	Collaboration on incubator operationalisation; sharing and replication of best practices; participation in cocreation sessions; engagement in regional innovation activities supporting SPMM related startups and applied R&D.	Partner channels (website and social media), regional innovation networks, incubator events, workshops, project website and LinkedIn account.
Qualification authorities and National Qualification Framework (NQF) representatives	Consultation on the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles; participation in accreditation and recognition discussions; review of guidance on ECTS/ECVET portability; engagement in policy dialogue on skill standardisation.	Policy briefs, targeted outreach, workshops, project website, newsletters.

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Stakeholder group	Engagement actions and activities	Main communication and dissemination channels
Policy makers and institutional decision-makers	Engagement in dialogue sessions on safety, environmental and economic impacts of SPMM; review of evidence-based recommendations; participation in events showcasing pilot results and societal benefits.	Policy briefs, newsletters, conferences, targeted mailings, project website, direct outreach.
Ecosystem catalysts (clusters, associations, technology parks)	Joint promotion of events and cross-sectoral activities; support for dissemination through partner networks; participation in matchmaking and knowledge exchange activities; amplification of incubator and training initiatives.	Partner networks, LinkedIn, newsletters, regional events, association channels, media features.
Underrepresented groups and diversity focused organisations	Engagement through the Women in Maritime Tech accelerator; participation in awareness campaigns promoting inclusive career pathways; involvement in mentorship and empowerment activities.	Social media (LinkedIn), project website, targeted outreach, diversity networks, events.
General public and civil society	Public communication on the societal benefits of SPMM; sharing of success stories and accessible explanations of maritime safety challenges; participation in open events promoting awareness of maritime digitalisation.	Project website, social media (LinkedIn), press releases, public events, newsletters.

4.6 Coordination, roles, and timing

The implementation of CD activities follows BLUEVISION’s overall timeline and its three-phase structure, ensuring that communication, dissemination, and exploitation actions evolve dynamically as project outputs mature and stakeholder engagement deepens.

During the **Creation phase** (Months 1–12), the focus lies on establishing BLUEVISION’s identity, launching initial communication activities, and publishing the micro-credential framework together with the first version of the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles. This phase also includes preparing operational guidance for the seven entrepreneurial maritime incubators and introducing the SPMM skills ecosystem platform and industrial metaverse concept to stakeholders.

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In the **Growth phase** (Months 13–24), dissemination and engagement intensify as micro-courses, incubators, and pilot activities become available. Trainer empowerment, incubator operationalisation, and the piloting of the SPMM skills ecosystem platform through 200 work-based learning apprenticeships form the core of this period. Stakeholder consultations, accreditation discussions and cross-regional collaboration expand significantly as partners begin integrating BLUEVISION outputs into their training and operational environments.

The **Exploitation phase** (Months 25–36) focuses on maximising impact and ensuring long-term sustainability. Activities centre on promoting formal recognition of the SPMM Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles, embedding micro-credentials into IVET and CVET offers, supporting incubator replication, and communicating consolidated policy recommendations and impact assessments to industry and policymakers.

The CD Plan will be initiated in Month 3 (M3) and updated in M12, M24, and M36 respectively to reflect project progress, stakeholder feedback, and emerging opportunities. Updates will incorporate monitoring insights aligned with the Control component of the 4Cs principles to ensure responsiveness and continuous improvement.

A dedicated WP7 team, composed of at least one representative from each consortium organisation, supports coordination and implementation. The team meets initially **on a bi-weekly basis and subsequently on a monthly basis** to:

- review progress on ongoing IDE actions;
- align activities with project milestones and outputs;
- monitor KPI achievement and update the performance dashboard; and
- ensure consistent messaging, branding, and visibility across all materials.

All partners actively contribute to IDE implementation according to their expertise. Partners are expected to propose content, participate in outreach activities, and support event organisation.

Communication within BLUEVISION further follows a combined centralised and decentralised model. Central coordination manages the project website, social media channels, and newsletters to ensure coherence, compliance with EU visibility requirements and alignment with strategic objectives. In parallel, partners with strong institutional or regional reach amplify project messages through their own channels, significantly extending outreach across national and sectoral boundaries.

To ensure balanced visibility and active participation, BLUEVISION applies a coordinated content-sharing approach in which partners contribute regularly to central communication channels as discussed in the regular WP7-related meetings. Based on ongoing project developments the respective dissemination activities can be conducted. Planning and transparency are supported through shared digital tools that allow partners to track upcoming communication activities, deadlines, and dissemination tasks.

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EIT Manufacturing East serves as the overall coordinator of IDE activities, responsible for ensuring coherence, alignment with project objectives, and compliance with European Commission requirements. EIT Manufacturing East oversees the practical implementation of the CD Plan, manages updates, and ensures that communication, dissemination, and exploitation remain integrated and mutually reinforcing. Below is the full list of consortium partners involved in the work package:

- ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS (CERTH)
- EIT Manufacturing East GmbH (EITM)
- YET MAKE (YET)
- K. KAI E. ZAFEIRIOU O.E. (ISALOS)
- HELIXCONNECT EUROPE SRL (HELIX)
- FOUNDATION WEGEMT — A EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF UNIVERSITIES IN MARINE TECHNOLOGY AND RELATED SCIENCES (WEGEMT)
- TECHNOLOGICAL CORPORATION OF ANDALUSIA (CTA)
- DEEP BLUE SRL (DB)
- CONSTANTA MARITIME UNIVERSITY (UMC)
- CENTRE FOR SUSTAINABILITY LTD (C4S)
- SUDOTIM AS SRL (SUDOTIM)
- AUTORITATEA NATIONALA PENTRU CALIFICARI-ANC (ANCRO)
- INSTITUTO LIMENIKIS KATARTISIS EXANTAS (EXANTAS)

This coordinated and structured approach guarantees that IDE actions are synchronised across the consortium, coherent in their messaging, and strategically integrated into the broader project objectives.

5 Tools, channels, and branding for outreach and engagement

The project will employ a comprehensive set of tools and communication channels to ensure effective outreach, engagement, and visibility across different target audiences. All materials and activities will adhere to a consistent project brand identity.

5.1 Visual identity and branding

A unified and recognisable visual identity will ensure a consistent and professional presentation of BLUEVISION across all materials, digital platforms, and stakeholder interactions. The identity will reflect the project's focus on Sustainable Predictive Maintenance (SPMM) for maritime infrastructures, its emphasis on safety, environmental benefits and workforce mobility, and its commitment to inclusive, human-centric innovation. The branding package will support clear, multilingual communication and compliance with EU visibility requirements.

The project branding package includes:

- **Project logo** for use across digital and print materials.

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

- **Comprehensive brand manual** providing guidance on logo usage, typography, colour palette, tone of voice, accessibility and compliance with EU visibility rules.
- **Standardised templates** for deliverables, reports and PowerPoint presentations to ensure consistent formatting and presentation.
- **Web and social media asset set**, including header images, profile banners and post templates to maintain a coherent online presence.
- **Multilingual and accessibility guidance** to support translation, localisation, and inclusive presentation of materials for diverse stakeholder groups.
- **Custom icon set** that visually supports key BLUEVISION themes such as SPMM, digital twins, incubators, apprenticeships and competence frameworks.

Colour codes:

The following colour palette defines BLUEVISION's visual identity and ensures consistency across digital and print materials. All colour applications must comply with accessibility standards (WCAG) to guarantee sufficient contrast and readability.

Primary colours in RGB format

- #30b5d3
- #58c8e4

Secondary colours

- #ffa69d
- #2fa4b7
- #5b8aa2

Dark base

- #0b2430

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Primary colours

Secondary colours

Dark base

Figure 2: BLUEVISION colour codes (status: 13.02.2026)

The primary colours should dominate the visual composition, while secondary colours should be used sparingly to maintain visual coherence.

5.1.1 Logo

The BLUEVISION logo combines geometric simplicity with maritime symbolism, reflecting the project's focus on Sustainable Predictive Maritime Maintenance (SPMM), immersive learning and human-centric innovation. A compact circular emblem anchors the mark, evoking systems, monitoring and continuous cycles central to predictive maintenance, while the blue colour palette signals the maritime context, trust, and technical reliability. Subtle internal geometry within the circle suggests lenses, radiating sensors or digital twin hubs, hinting at observation, simulation and hands-on learning; the clean, modern wordmark grounds the emblem in clarity and accessibility for diverse audiences.

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

Together these shared features communicate BLUEVISION's mission to make maritime operations safer, more sustainable and more skill-driven, while remaining flexible for application across digital platforms, training materials and institutional communications.

Figure 3: BLUEVISION logo (status: 19.02.2026)

5.1.2 Brand manual

The brand manual provides clear and practical guidance for maintaining a consistent visual and verbal identity across all communication materials. It covers every aspect of the brand, from tone of voice and messaging style to logo use, colour palette, and typography. The manual has been shared with all consortium partners via SharePoint to ensure consistent application across all communication materials. It will also be made publicly available on the project website to support transparency and alignment with the Horizon Europe visibility requirements.

5.1.3 Standardised templates for deliverables, reports, and PowerPoint presentations

A set of standardised templates has been developed for deliverables, reports, and PowerPoint presentations to ensure a unified and professional visual style. These templates follow the project's branding guidelines, incorporating the logo, colour palette, and typography, and are mandatory for use by all partners in official project outputs, ensuring consistency and compliance with EU visibility requirements.

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Figure 4: BLUEVISION PowerPoint template (status: 25.02.2026)

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

BLUEVISION

DX.X TITLE

Sustainable predictive maintenance for circular material preservation and human-centric remote-operations in maritime critical infrastructures via augmented reality and digital twins
BLUEVISION

Project acronym:	BLUEVISION
Project topic:	ERASMUS-EDU-2025-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP
Project number:	101244912
Type of action:	ERASMUS Lump Sum Grants
Project starting date:	1 December 2025
Project duration:	36 months
Dissemination level	PU, SEN (choose applicable level)

Disclaimer: BLUEVISION is a project funded by the European Union under the Erasmus+ call ERASMUS-EDU-2025-PI-ALL-INNO under Grant Agreement n° 101244912.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

All the contributors to this deliverable declare that they:

- Are aware that plagiarism and/or literal utilisation (copy) of materials and texts from other Projects, works and deliverables must be avoided and may be subject to disciplinary actions against the related partners and/or the Project consortium by the EU.
- Confirm that all their individual contributions to this deliverable are genuine and their own work or the work of their teams working in the Project, except where is explicitly indicated otherwise. GenAI tools may have been used to support text refinement. However, all content has been carefully reviewed and edited to ensure accuracy, originality and adherence to project standards.
- Have followed the required conventions in referencing the thoughts, ideas and texts made outside the Project.

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Deliverable Title Version

Work package:	
Deliverable number:	
Due date:	
Submission date:	
Start date of project:	
Duration of project:	
Lead beneficiary:	
Version:	
Status:	
Author name(s):	
Reviewer(s):	
Nature:	
Dissemination level:	

Nature	Dissemination level
R = Report P = Prototype D = Demonstrator DEC = Websites, patent, filings, videos, etc O = Other	PU = Public SEN = Sensitive

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments

Document ID
BLUEVISION internal reports coding
Partner abbreviation
Nature
Work package
Task
Version
e.g. EITM_R_WP7_7.1_V1 (Report on Task 7.1 of the Work package 7 first version delivered by EIT Manufacturing (This section is included for demonstration purposes only. Please remove it once the document is finalised, as it is not part of the official content.))

Figure 5: BLUEVISION template for deliverables (status: 11.02.2026)

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

5.1.4 Stock image library

BLUEVISION adopts a dual imagery approach that balances technological depth with a humancentred perspective, reflecting both the project's focus on Sustainable Predictive Maritime Maintenance (SPMM) and the people who operate, maintain and benefit from maritime systems. A curated stock image library will be maintained for consortium use, organised around three core themes: **SPMM and digital twins**, **maritime safety and environmental resilience**, and **people, skills and career pathways**. Images will be selected to support multilingual materials, training and outreach, and to ensure consistent, highquality visuals across communications and deliverables. The collection will be made available to all partners for project related use and will be expanded as communication needs evolve to keep visual content relevant throughout the project lifetime.

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

Figure 6: BLUEVISION stock image library examples (status: 11.02.2026)

5.1.5 Icons

A custom **icon set** has been created to visually support key concepts and strengthen the project's visual identity. The icons are designed to complement other brand elements and ensure a coherent look across all materials and communication channels. The current set is foundational and will be expanded as new communication needs arise. All icons are available to consortium partners for use in project presentations, publications, and online content.

Figure 7: BLUEVISION icons set (status 11.02.2026)

5.1.6 Promotional materials

A comprehensive set of promotional materials will support the project's communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring coherent visibility across all outreach actions. The package will include printed and digital materials such as:

- brochures/flyers
- roll-up banners
- factsheets
- posters
- branded giveaways (used at events, conferences, and stakeholder meetings)

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These materials will be designed in line with the project's visual identity and the EU visibility guidelines, maintaining consistency with the logo, colour palette, and typography defined in the brand manual. All materials will be made available to consortium partners through the shared repository for local adaptation and use in national or institutional outreach activities.

5.2 Project website and platform

5.2.1 Project website

The BLUEVISION website will serve as the project's central information, and engagement hub, presenting learning offers, incubator activities, pilot evidence and open resources in a clear, multilingual format (accessible in the following languages: EN, RO, GR, IT, ES, DE, NL). It will be designed for accessibility, mobile responsiveness, and easy navigation so that frontline maritime workers, trainers, industry partners and policy stakeholders can quickly find relevant materials and participation routes.

Website link: to be added once finalised

Main sections

- **Home** — Overview of BLUEVISION's vision and mission; consortium members (e.g.: via logo carousel); newsletter subscription; clear EU funding acknowledgment; imprint, privacy policy and cookie policy.
- **About** — Project background, objectives and how to achieve them, expected impact, SPMM context and key definitions; short descriptions of the micro-credential framework, Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles.
- **Communication toolkit** — Downloadable assets for partners (logo, brand manual summary, flyer and roll-up banner templates, social media post templates).
- **Courses and workshops** — Presentation of the seven ECTS/ECVET-aligned micro-courses, trainer academies and lifelong learning materials; links to the Marketplace/ Learning Management System (LMS) for enrolment and trainer resources.
- **Incubators and pilots** — Overview of the seven entrepreneurial maritime incubators, operational guidance, demonstrator summaries and opportunities for industry collaboration and apprenticeships.
- **SPMM skills ecosystem platform** — Introduction to the skills ecosystem, digital twins and industrial metaverse features; signposting to platform access and pilot participation.
- **Media** — Press releases, event section including registrations, event reports with photos, partner interviews and testimonials.
- **Content hub** — Repository of key outputs: micro-credential framework, Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles, policy briefs, case studies and open access reports.
- **Contact** — Dedicated contact form for external enquiries, partnership requests and accreditation queries.

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5.2.2 Online platform for courses and workshops

The BLUEVISION courses will be hosted on the dedicated BLUEVISION platform managed by YET and on the [Deep Tech Talent Initiative \(DTTI\) website](#). The platform will provide a single, user-friendly environment for delivering the seven ECTS/ECVET aligned micro-courses, trainer academies, and complementary lifelong learning materials, supporting both self-paced and blended learning pathways.

5.3 Social media and newsletters

BLUEVISION will maintain an active, coordinated online presence centred on a project LinkedIn account and a regular newsletter to maximise outreach, share pilot evidence, promote training opportunities, and engage frontline maritime workers, trainers, incubator partners, industry stakeholders, and policy audiences. EIT Manufacturing East will centrally manage the LinkedIn account and newsletter production to ensure consistent messaging, EU visibility requirements and editorial quality. All partners will amplify content through their institutional channels to extend regional and sectoral reach. Analytics and IDE KPIs used to monitor engagement and guide content priorities.

5.3.1 LinkedIn

Rationale for selection

LinkedIn is the leading professional network for research and innovation stakeholders. It enables targeted outreach to academics, policymakers, and industry representatives and is ideal for fostering dialogue on maritime-related topics, building partnerships, and sharing insights in a professional context.

Posting formats

- Project and milestone announcements
- Partner and talent stories
- Event invitations and summaries
- Save the dates
- Post event content
- Collaboration with other EU projects or initiatives

Engagement style

Moderate use of emojis to attract attention, combined with relevant hashtags for discoverability. Partners are encouraged to tag institutions and stakeholders to extend reach.

Suggested hashtags: #SPMM #BLUEVISION #MaritimeInnovation #TalentDevelopment #Industry5_0 #Microcredentials #EUprojects #GreenTransition #BlueEconomy

D7.1 Communication and Dissemination plan

Example LinkedIn post

🔗 Exciting milestone for BLUEVISION!

Our first pilot is live, connecting industry, trainers and apprentices to advance human-centric Sustainable Predictive Maintenance in maritime operations.

Discover how digital twins, immersive learning and our micro-credential pathway are turning research into on-the-job skills and career opportunities

👉 [link] @Partner1 @Partner2

Example visual:

5.3.2 Newsletters

Rationale for selection

Newsletters are a key part of the project's communication ecosystem, providing transparent and inclusive updates that strengthen stakeholder engagement and reflect RRI principles of openness and accountability. They make project outcomes accessible to both experts and the wider public.

The newsletter strategy combines centralised and decentralised dissemination, integrating both project-driven and partner-driven formats to maximise visibility.

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1. Project-driven newsletter

Coordinated by EIT Manufacturing East and published through the project website and/or LinkedIn, this semi-annual newsletter compiles key results, milestones, and upcoming opportunities, maintaining consistency in tone, design, and branding. It serves as the project's main public communication outlet. Furthermore, existing newsletters managed by EIT Manufacturing such as "Manufacturing Reads", the newsletter of EIT Manufacturing East, or the monthly EIT Manufacturing events newsletter via LinkedIn will be used to promote relevant activities and milestones to interested stakeholders.

2. Partner-driven newsletters

Several consortium partners with large institutional networks, will issue their own newsletters to complement central project communication.

Both formats are complementary: the project-driven newsletter ensures unity and compliance with EU visibility requirements, while partner-driven newsletters broaden impact through established communication ecosystems. Together, they strengthen openness, inclusiveness, and mutual learning across Europe's research and innovation landscape.

5.3.3 Emojis and hashtags

Using emojis

Incorporating emojis into social media posts can significantly enhance communication effectiveness:

- Visual appeal: emojis make posts more eye-catching and help content stand out in crowded feeds, increasing the chance that frontline maritime workers, trainers, and industry contacts pause to read.
- Tone and emotion: emojis convey tone and humanise messages, making technical topics like SPMM and digital twins feel more relatable and accessible.
- Clarity and emphasis: simple emojis can highlight calls to action (e.g., signups, course launches, event dates) and draw attention to key facts or metrics without adding extra text.
- Audience fit: choose emojis that resonate with maritime and vocational audiences (e.g., 🚢, 📚, 🎓, 🔍) while avoiding overly casual or ambiguous symbols.
- Accessibility and moderation: use emojis sparingly and consistently; ensure meaning remains clear for screen-reader users by placing emojis after short, descriptive text and not relying on them to convey essential information.
- Brand tone alignment: select emoji styles that match BLUEVISION's professional, human-centred tone, supportive, practical and inclusive, rather than playful or sensational.

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Using hashtags

- Increase visibility: hashtags categorise content and make it discoverable to users searching for topics like maritime safety, skills and micro-credentials.
- Topical reach: combine broad sector tags (e.g., #MaritimeInnovation) with project specific tags (e.g. #BLUEVISION) and campaign tags (e.g., #SPMMPilot) to reach different audience layers.
- Brand awareness: consistently use a core branded hashtag (#BLUEVISION) to build recognition and encourage partners and stakeholders to tag related posts.
- Campaign amplification: coordinate hashtag uses across partners during semi-annual campaigns to maximise collective reach and make analytics easier to aggregate.
- Contextual tagging: add event or output specific tags for launches, webinars, or publications (e.g., #Microcredentials, #DigitalTwinDemo) to group related posts and support follow-up searches.
- Governance and review: maintain a short, approved hashtag list in the brand manual; review and update it annually to reflect evolving project activities and emerging sector terms.

Core set of hashtags (BLUEVISION)

- #BLUEVISION
- #SPMM
- #MaritimeInnovation
- #Microcredentials
- #DigitalTwin
- #SustainableShipping
- #Industry5_0
- #TalentDevelopment
- #VET
- #Skills
- #HorizonEU
- #MaritimeSafety
- #Apprenticeships
- #DigitalTransformation
- #EUprojects
- #GreenTransition
- #BlueEconomy

The hashtag list is indicative and will be reviewed annually to ensure continued relevance and alignment with BLUEVISION's evolving activities and strategic communication priorities.

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5.3.4 Social media rotation policy

To ensure consistent, balanced, and engaging communication across all project channels, the BLUEVISION project implements a social media rotation policy coordinated by EITM. This policy guarantees that all partners actively contribute to the project's online presence while maintaining a steady publication rhythm in line with the Grant Agreement commitment of at least one post per week.

Under this system, two partners are assigned each month to provide content for the official project social media channels. These partners share responsibility for preparing short posts, visuals, or news items highlighting project milestones, partner activities, events, or related initiatives. EITM reviews and schedules this content to ensure coherence in tone, style, and branding.

While two partners are assigned each month, all consortium members are encouraged to contribute additional content at any time. This open contribution model helps capture ongoing developments across the project and strengthens overall visibility and engagement. The rotation policy ensures that:

- each partner has equal visibility and representation on project channels;
- a continuous and diverse flow of content is maintained throughout the year;
- communication responsibilities are evenly distributed across the consortium;
- the project's key achievements, talents, and events are showcased regularly and inclusively.

This structured yet flexible approach balances coordination with creativity, allowing all partners to take ownership of the project's communication while ensuring reliability and compliance with European Commission (EC) communication commitments.

The project uses a dedicated **MS Teams Planner "Work Package 7"** to coordinate this process. The planner serves as an interactive communication calendar where all partners can view upcoming posts, assigned months, and content themes. This tool enables real-time collaboration, transparency, and planning across the consortium, allowing everyone to stay informed about current and scheduled communication activities.

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Figure 8: BLUEVISION Planner "Work Package 7" (status: 11.02.2026)

6 Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation are central to ensuring that CD activities are effective, measurable, and aligned with project objectives. Continuous tracking allows the consortium to demonstrate progress, assess impact, and adapt its approach as needed.

Implementation of the CD Plan will be continuously monitored under the *Curation* and *Control* elements of the 4Cs principles. Monitoring ensures transparency, accountability, and data-driven management of all CD activities, while *Curation* guarantees that information is collected, validated, and presented consistently across the consortium.

To support systematic tracking, the project has developed a **Communication Dashboard**, designed in an Excel format and shared with all partners. This dashboard provides a common reporting framework aligned with the European Commission's mandatory fields in the Funding & Tenders Portal. It serves as the central internal tool for documenting, analysing, and reporting IDE performance across the consortium, facilitating timely adjustments and informed decision-making.

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in the EC portal, avoiding sporadic entries and ensuring a coherent, quality-assured record of project achievements.

To complement the Communication Dashboard, the project will use altimetric tools and analytics to monitor the online visibility and engagement of its outputs. These tools will track how project results are shared and discussed across digital platforms, providing evidence of their broader societal reach.

The monitored indicators will include:

- number of shares and mentions on social media platforms (such as LinkedIn);
- repository downloads and dataset views from open-access sources like Zenodo and GitHub;
- public engagement metrics such as unique website visitors, newsletter subscriptions, and event participation.

Findings from the dashboard, KPI tracking, and Open Science monitoring will feed into CD reviews. These reviews will assess progress, evaluate performance against targets, and propose updates to enhance visibility, efficiency, and impact. Adjustments will be made to reflect new opportunities, stakeholder feedback, and the evolving project context.

This adaptive and data-driven approach ensures that all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities remain relevant, coherent, and aligned with the project's objectives. It also guarantees that all actions are traceable, measurable, and compliant with European Commission reporting and Open Science requirements.

6.1 Indicators of success – Key Performance Indicators and Key Exploitable results

The project integrates both **Key Performance Indicators** and **Key Exploitable Results** to ensure that dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities are not only measurable but also strategically linked to the project's tangible outputs. While KPIs provide a high-level overview of progress and performance across all IDE activities, KERs represent concrete, outcome-oriented results with potential for scientific, societal, or commercial use. Together, they form a complementary monitoring framework where KPIs track the effectiveness and reach of actions, and KERs assess the quality, uptake, and sustainability of the project's achievements.

6.2 Key Performance Indicators

Likes/Reactions, Comments, and Reposts

Likes and reactions represent the number of people who have engaged with a BLUEVISION post at a basic level. These interactions signal that the content resonated with viewers as they scrolled through their feed. Comments provide a deeper layer of engagement: while reactions are quick and effortless, a comment indicates that the audience member has something meaningful to contribute, making it a stronger indicator of interest in the project's themes such as SPMM, digital twins, micro-credentials, or maritime skills development.

Reposts are the strongest form of engagement, as they show that a user values the content enough to share it with their own network. For BLUEVISION, reposts are particularly valuable because they extend the project's visibility to maritime workers, VET communities, companies, and policymakers who may

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not yet follow the project directly. Partners are therefore encouraged to regularly repost content from the BLUEVISION LinkedIn channel to maximise reach and strengthen the decentralised communication model, contributing to measurable growth in engagement and audience expansion.

7 Engagement Rate

Engagement rate measures how actively the audience interacts with BLUEVISION content relative to the size of the audience. It is typically calculated by adding all reactions (likes, comments, shares, etc.) and dividing this total by the number of followers, then multiplying by 100 to obtain a percentage.

However, not all followers will see every post, and engagement may also come from users who do not follow the BLUEVISION account (for example, through partner reposts). This means engagement rates can appear lower than the true level of interest. Nevertheless, engagement rate remains a key indicator for social media algorithms, which reward high engagement content with increased visibility.

To contextualise BLUEVISION's performance, sector benchmarks on LinkedIn (as of 2024) show:

- **Education sector:** ~1.8%
- **Construction, Mining & Manufacturing:** ~2.7%
- **Technology sector:** ~2.4%

Given BLUEVISION's cross-sector positioning (maritime, VET, digital innovation), a reasonable target engagement rate is **approximately 2.3%**.

This benchmark will help guide content optimisation and ensure that BLUEVISION's communication activities remain competitive and effective within the LinkedIn ecosystem.

The following table provides an overview of all KPIs established for the IDE activities within the project. KPIs are monitored through the **Communication Dashboard (see Section 6)** and updated during the **annual CD review**.

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Table 1: CD KPIs

KPI Description	Description	Indicator performance	Indicator goal	Progress	Measurement	Responsible partner
Write the specific Key Performance Indicator you are tracking	Briefly explain what this KPI measures	Enter the current result or value for this KPI	Specify the target or benchmark	Describe progress toward the goal	Explain how this KPI is measured	
Website views	5,000 visits on website reached per year	0	15,000	0%	Website analytics	
Social Media engagements	100,000 engagements reached by the end of project	0	100,000	0%	LinkedIn analytics	
	Mailing list with certain number of contacts	0	30,000	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Newsletter Number of contacts	0	10,000	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Newsletters published	0	6	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Promotional videos	0	6	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Open Day events organised (2 per country)	0	14	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Participants reached at Open days	0	500	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Policy makers	0	20	0%	Numbers submitted	

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	engaged at open days				by project partners	
	BLUEVISION platform with qualified contacts	0	1,000	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	TV and radio appearances	0	6	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	
	Citizen's reached via TV and radio appearances	0	1,000,000	0%	Numbers submitted by project partners	

7.1 Key Exploitable Results

BLUEVISION is committed to fostering a holistic approach to ensure sustainability for its outputs. Rather than treating each result as a standalone commercialisable unit, BLUEVISION integrates the synergistic qualities of its outputs to concentrate on the sustainability, reusability, and commercial viability.

Access to the results/products will be freely available, with exceptions for the certification awarding process and the Industrial Metaverse Simulation tool, which will operate under a subscription model due to their external development and operational costs, unless publicly funded sponsorships are secured.

BLUEVISION will be commercialised through a joint venture partnership with all partners, under an agreement managed by CERTH, ensuring that ownership of background intellectual property (IP) remains with the originating partner, with royalty-free access granted for project capacity building. Ownership of foreground IP rests with the creator, yet partners will grant each other unrestricted, free access for project objectives. The consortium is dedicated to adhering to the EU's Open Access mandates, making use of all appropriate Open Access channels and repositories.

Table 2: KER CD matrix

Key Exploitable Result	Type of exploitation	Further maintained?	Resources needed for further development
Blueprint of the Entrepreneurial Maritime Incubator concept	Service fee	Yes	Public grants to support partnership development and direct sales to other centres that aim to open such incubators.

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Women accelerator in maritime tech	Service fee + Licence fee per user	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.
BLUEVISION Digital Platform	Free of charge (general access)	Yes	Partners' cofinancing and eventually further grants.
Maritime Industrial Metaverse Simulation Platform	Service fee + Licence fee per user	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.
Training toolkits & micro-credentials (for all target groups)	Free access to the content + service fee for the certification	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.
Learner analytics tool	Licence fee per user	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.
Market skill gaps analytics tool	Licence fee per user	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.
Regional impact measurement tool	Licence fee per user	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.
Future of SPMM work report & policy guidelines (pan-EU skills portability guide) including the competence framework and occupational profiles guidelines for the future SPMM labour	Licence fee per user. Service fee in case additional work is requested.	Yes	Direct sales + further sponsored options in case of grants received.

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8 Exploitation plan

8.1 Revenue Streams & Business Model:

STEP 0: (during the project lifecycle): BLUEVISION will engage in agreements/partnerships with: ports, ship operators, offshore platform operator, underwater infrastructure operators, universities and VET centres providing training in the maritime sector in order to devise joint partnerships for future SPMM upskilling delivery and for SPMM innovation co-creation (see Table 3.5 for a list of entities considered for partnership). All outputs aim to motivate companies to invest in BLUEVISION services and to engage them in providing digital twins of their processes for the industrial metaverse simulation platform.

STEP 1: (0-2 years post-project lifecycle). Secure at least four EU-funded projects annually per country, with a minimum total value of EUR 500,000 each, to support the operational and institutional growth of BLUEVISION services. Targeted calls will include Horizon Europe WIDERA Excellence Hubs, Cluster 4, INTERREG, and Erasmus+ Centres of Vocational Excellence. Applications will be made both jointly and independently, led by HELIX, while seeking synergies with similar projects to optimize results and funding efficiency. Leveraging results and lessons learned from similar initiatives, BLUEVISION will enhance its services, extend its impact, and contribute to a cohesive ecosystem of educational and technological innovation.

Post-EU funding, impact will be sustained through a multifaceted strategy focused on continuous improvement, collaboration, and commercial viability. Establishing regional BLUEVISION Incubators will further enhance capabilities and foster public-private investment, ensuring long-term sustainability. Particularly, a strong focus will be set on securing regional funds (Smart Specialisation Strategies) to support the development of publicly funded competence centres in maritime matters.

STEP 2: (1-3 years post-project lifecycle & beyond). Promote the BLUEVISION Platform broadly and generate revenue through service and certification fees, focusing on the Key Exploitable Results outlined in Table 3.6. This effort will be led by CTA and EITM, supported by all partners, with the option of maintaining free access (up to a 15% quota).

The DTTI platform will be utilized as the primary outreach channel to recruit learners at a pan-EU level. Each partner will maintain strong connections with public authorities to secure public investment. Broad promotion of BLUEVISION will target at least 500 users per year per incubator, ensuring both revenue generation and social impact. BLUEVISION certifications will be positioned as a recognised standard for SPMM certification at regional and national levels, attracting industrial clients and reinforcing commercial viability, workforce development, and long-term impact.

STEP 3: (1-5 years post-project lifecycle & beyond). Organize an annual BLUEVISION Conference bringing together training providers, maritime stakeholders, SPMM and cleantech technology providers, stakeholders supporting learners and workers from social groups at risk, certification bodies, and policymakers. These conferences will mobilize a large regional stakeholder network around each

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incubator, fostering the continuous creation and growth of a community of practice centred around the Skills Ecosystems developed.

The conferences (with registration fees) will generate revenue for each incubator and provide an opportunity to showcase past successes. Additionally, they will serve as a platform to celebrate talent, offer awards to top performers, and promote inclusive, representative role models to actively encourage inclusion in VET and higher education within the maritime sector.

STEP 4: (2-5 years post-project lifecycle & beyond). With adequate funding, further developing of the BLUEVISION Platform by introducing smart EdTech solutions (BLUEVISION platform 2.0), featuring AI-driven personalized learning, blockchain-based micro-credentials, and augmented reality applications for industrial metaverse simulations (expanding the number of digital twins). This will streamline service provision and revenue generation while contributing to technological development, leading to the creation of Deep Tech Skills Ecosystems around each incubator. CERTH will lead this sustainability process, collaborating with incubator leaders to ensure the feasibility and scalability of these advancements.

STEP 5: (3-5 years post-project lifecycle & beyond). Position BLUEVISION certifications, test-beds (infrastructure), and tools as a recognised standard for SPMM certification and excellence at regional and national levels. This approach will secure a steady influx of industrial clients for workforce certification, in collaboration with universities and VET centres. Certification points will be marketed as both initial training and reskilling, addressing diverse regional needs. EITM will lead this process, ensuring widespread adoption and recognition. On top of this, the objective is to achieve full recognition of the SPMM micro-credential across all EU countries (leveraging the policy work on pan-EU skill portability and the efforts to accept the BLUEVISION SPMM competence framework an occupational profile across the EU). This also entails integration of the profiles in ESCO and devising a unified SPMM occupational profile. At this stage, efforts will be taken to expand the reach of the incubators and BLUEVISION platform beyond the EU (particularly in international maritime markets).

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8.2 Overall outreach (visibility) to key stakeholders and funding acquisition predictions summary

Table 3 – High-level governmental visibility (dissemination for sustainability) & funding

Level	Type of Partner	Type of Funding
Regional Level	Regional Development Agencies in Charge of Smart Specialisation and Education 25% of Regional VET Centres and Universities	Public: ERDF – committed by the regional development agencies. Private: Training services/fees paid by companies that need skilled labour.
National Level	Ministries of Labour, Education, Innovation, Digitalisation and Energy.	Public: National-level funding for establishing large-scale regional centres (space, equipment, national validation).
EU Level	Upskilling EU platforms/agencies: CEDEFOP, ESCO, EACEA, EPALE for VET, European Digital Credential Platform. Sectoral EU-wide associations Cross-border EU programmes (INTERREG)	Public: INTERREG, EU-wide tenders, Erasmus+, Horizon Europe. Private: Training services/fees paid by companies that need skilled labour.

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Conclusion

This Communication and Dissemination (CD) Plan provides a comprehensive framework to maximise the visibility, accessibility, and long-term impact of BLUEVISION results. It outlines a strategic, phased approach that ensures all dissemination, exploitation, and communication actions are coherent, targeted, and aligned with the overall project objectives.

Through consistent branding, targeted messaging, and diverse communication channels, the plan ensures that project results effectively reach academic, industrial, policy, and societal audiences. The implementation of monitoring tools, including the Communication Dashboard, Key Performance Indicators, and altimetric analytics, will enable continuous evaluation and adaptation to maintain high-quality and evidence-based management of all activities.

Exploitation planning will be further developed through a structured multi-step process involving partner surveys, SWOT analyses, joint workshops, and business model design, ensuring that Key Exploitable Results are systematically assessed and guided toward sustainable use.

Overall, this plan serves as a practical roadmap for coordinated, inclusive, and impactful dissemination, exploitation, and communication throughout the project's lifetime, laying the foundation for continued visibility, collaboration, and uptake of results beyond the project's duration.

Annex 1: To-market approach questionnaire

The following table presents a preliminary draft of the To-market approach questionnaire, which will serve as the basis for developing the final version to be distributed to partners. This initial version is designed to outline the key areas of inquiry and guide the collection of essential information related to each KER. The refined questionnaire, to be released in M6, will be aligned with the project's exploitation framework and used to gather structured input from all partners to support the development of Deliverable D7.1.

Section	Question / Description	Partner Input
1. Result overview	Briefly describe your result or solution (e.g. product, service, process, training, policy recommendation, publication).	
2. Problem addressed	What specific problem or need does your result address? Who experiences this problem?	
3. Alternative solutions	How is this problem currently being solved or addressed? What are the limitations of existing approaches?	
4. Unique value proposition (UVP)	What makes your result unique or superior? What are its key benefits and innovative features compared to alternatives?	

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5. Target market	Describe the market or user segment(s) where your solution will be applied. Who are the main customers and early adopters?	
6. Competitors	Identify main competitors or comparable solutions. What are their strengths and weaknesses relative to your result?	
7. Market size and trends	Estimate the potential size and growth of your market. What trends or developments are shaping this field?	
8. Impact and acceptance	Assess expected social, environmental, and economic impacts. What is the expected level of public or stakeholder acceptance?	
9. Legal, ethical, and normative context	Are there any legal, ethical, or normative conditions that influence the use or deployment of your result?	
10. Use model (go-to-market approach)	How will the result be used or made available (e.g. product manufacturing, service provision, licensing, technology transfer, publication, etc.)?	
11. Intellectual property	Identify background and foreground IP relevant to this result. Which partner(s) own or contribute to it?	
12. Early adopters	Who are your first potential users or adopters, and how can they be reached?	
13. Pricing and business model	If applicable, estimate potential pricing or cost recovery model. What would be the breakeven point?	
14. Time to market	How long will it take to make the solution available to its users after project completion?	
15. Implementation capacity	Do the partners involved have the necessary skills and resources to bring the result to market or practical use?	
16. External partners (if needed)	Do you require additional partners or expertise for exploitation? If yes, what type?	